

Brief Dissemination and Communication (D&C) Plan for our OASES Consortium Network

Introduction

In our OASES project, Helwan University (HU) partner is the leader of WP5 “Dissemination, demonstration, and capacity building” supported by all partners. Therefore, it is HU role to set up a proper plan for the dissemination, relevant communication, and the process of implementation among our OASES partners and networks. It is confirmed that dissemination and relevant communication are vital for sharing and adopting OASES results and research outcomes to wider stakeholders and audiences among our network (individuals, organization, and institutions). This is also important for a long term sustainability success towards the practice-based research networks (PBRNs). Strategically, our OASES (D&C) plan should be linked as strong as possible with other EU research projects programs (especially LEAP RE). Because, the (D&C) are very much linked, the suggested plan will deal with “D&C” as one set in mind to achieve the maximum benefits and impact. The plan set is supported by essential activities including: defining the proper audiences and stakeholders, purpose, proper communication channels, dissemination tools, and evaluation process.

To ensure the success of the suggested dissemination and communication plan, it is absolutely necessary to consult all partners and the steering committee for approval.

Thanks to Fraunhofer, leader of the project (Doron and Jan), it is important to remind all OASES partners that a great Web site for OASES: <https://www.leap-re.eu/oases/> has been established. We will make sure that all the activities of the (D&C) will be integrated and feeding the proper input to this Web site to maximize the dissemination and impact.

I. OASES Dissemination and Communication Plan

The suggested plan is based on the following basic pillars:

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|--------------------------|----------------|
| i) Stakeholder analysis, | ii) Purpose |
| iii) Audiences, | iv) Messages |
| v) Methods (Tools), | vi) Time lines |
| vii) Evaluation | |

i. **OASES Stakeholder:** OASES partners should understand and identify the stakeholder’s preference and the real needs of interest. It is also important to include other active (PBRNs) programs and policy makers if possible. Examining the nature of our OASES indicates that the target stakeholders in EU and Africa are: OASES institutions and researchers, relevant RE organizations and industries, SMEs, relevant R&D labs or centers, and related ministries.

ii. **Purpose:** It is essentially important to define the directives of the (D&C) plan to outreach smoothly the stakeholders (messages, Methods, and timing). For our OASES project, the purpose of the (D&C) is obvious and includes:

- Raising the awareness of the relevant stakeholders and inject them with the knowledge of our OASES project.
- Promoting and selling OASES products (output results)
- Inform, educate, and engage the relevant community if possible.

iii. Audience:

Depending on the target audiences and their influences, the (D&C) process of OASES can be established. Based on the analysis exercised so far in OASES, our target audiences include different individuals in OASES consortium, different public authorities, different organizations, and relevant PBRNs. In our OASES (R&C), the following audience categories are considered:

- a) **Internal audiences:** These are OASES partners members (Team) including specially the steering committee. These audiences and their institutions should be well informed about OASES activities and progress results to ensure the project’s portfolio among the broad PBRNs.
- b) **External audiences:** These are the outreached stakeholders that should be benefited from OASES results (outcomes) specially those are working in the RE fields in different institutions, organizations, ministries, industries, SMEs, in addition to external viewers working in social media, librarians, ..etc. This audience class can act as multipliers for OASES dissemination and sharing the useful findings and results.
- c) **Relevant PBRNs:** It is of great importance to share OASES outcomes with other PBRNs key persons in similar RE projects such as: **PyPSA, SpineOpt, Backbone.** This will enhance OASES performance based on exchanging the experience, common problems discussion, and the PBRNs feedback.

iv) Messages: Based on the purpose and well defined audiences of OASES “D&C”, the key messages carrying clear and useful information of OASES activities progress and results can be communicated to the target audiences, stakeholders and relevant PBRNs as clarified before. It should be understood that our messages should be easy to understand, simple, and using a proper language for the target audiences. In addition, the D&C messages should carry correct and realistic information regarding OASES findings and outcomes.

v) Methods: It is recognized that there are substantial “D&C” methods, therefore we should select the most proper messages to serve the target audiences and realize OASES purposes. Of special interest, the following methods are adopted for OASES “D&C”:

- a) Regular flyers, newsletters, and press issues are used to raise OASES awareness.
- b) Web sites, Journal articles, Videos, and reports are used to disseminate OASES information.
- c) OASES presentations delivered at different conferences and Web sites are useful to promote our project’s results and outcomes.
- d) Workshops for OASES stakeholders, Webinars, or online meetings for discussion can foster the stakeholder’s involvement in our OASES and reduce resistance.

vi) Timing: In the suggested OASES (D&C), the time lines for the related activities depend largely on the rate of OASES progress and the equipped time of the target audiences. We should decide the relevant activities that are mostly of the audiences’ interest to receive.

Typically, raising the awareness of OASES will be at the beginning, while at the end, the focus will be on clarifying the useful outputs and deliverables.

It is wised to consider the messages receivers vacations and holidays specially the academic staffs and researchers at busy days of exams and other occasions.

vii) Evaluation of the (D&C)

To measure the degree of success of OASES “D&C”, it is helpful to implement an evaluation regime into the “D &C” activities such as Web sites logs in visitors, proper questionnaires for training programs, publications citations numbers, newsletters circulations numbers, feedback from the audiences, etc.

II. Action plan of OASES “D&C”

The proposed action plan will be active only after the approval of OASES steering committee. The following Table (1) illustrates a summary of the action plan of OASES “D&C” over the three years period of the project:

Table (1) Action plan of OASES “D&C” over three years period

Phases of the action	Objective of the action	Method	Target audience	Responsible partner	Due date
Phase-1: OASES awareness Period frame: (M01 - M12)	- D&C approval. - Establishing the starting awareness of OASES.	- Mailing list campaign, - Project’s Website, - News letter, - Promo materials, - Presentations, - Stakeholders events.	- OASES partners - All stakeholders - All stake holders - All stake holders - All stake holders - RE authorities utilities, and ministries(AF/EU)	- HU - Fraunhofer - HU - CDER - HU, Uni Ven	-ASAP -Already done -Semi annually -Semi annually -Semi annually -Semi annually
Phase 2: Directives and information (M13 - M24)	-Awareness targets for typical results and findings. - Information of the ultimate OASES goals that are of interest to the audiences.	- Promotional materials; - Message to the stake holders (project’s results so far) - Sharing stakeholders events to initiate cooperation.	- All stakeholders - All stakeholders - All stakeholders	- CDER, and Fraunhofer - HU, VTT, Uni KS and CSIR - All partners	-Semi annually -Semi annually - Annually
Phase 3: Outcomes (Exploitation) (M25 – M36)	- Target groups selection for OASES application. - Share the final outcomes. - Capacity building	- Communication to select special stakeholders; - Integration with other Leap RE projects: PyPSA, SpineOpt, Backbone. - WS for the final outcomes , - Special training programs and case studies - Final conference organization.	- Relevant authorities and ministries, - All stakeholders, - All stakeholders, - AF and EU institutions’ researchers, R&D centers of RE, M.Sc. and PhD students in RE fields (AF/ EU). - All stakeholders,	- Fraunhofer, VTT, and Uni KS -Uni KS, CSIR - HU, CDER, CSIR, Fraunhofer and VTT - HU, CDER, and all other partners -HU, Fraunhofer	-Last 6 months of OASES. -Last 6 months of OASES. -Last 3 months of OASES -Last 3 months of OASES -Last 3 months of OASES